

**The Change in Pollutant Levels Over the Bahamas Before
and After Hurricane Dorian**

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Abstract

Evaluating pollutant levels over regions of the earth is essential to the health of the humans that inhabit them. Being mindful of pollutants leads to the question: How are those pollutants affected by certain natural phenomena, such as hurricanes? Considering the effects of Hurricane Dorian on the levels of certain pollutants above the Bahamas sheds some light on this question. This research project attempts to consider several pollutants, such as CO, NO₂, HCHO, and aerosols, and comes to the conclusion that there is a significant increase in the presence of these pollutants shortly after the presence of Hurricane Dorian. An analysis of S5P Tropomi instrument's aerosol index data shows a substantial increase in the index both in the 340-380nm and 354-388nm ranges. In the days immediately following the storm, both CO and aerosols saw an increase in their column densities immediately after a significant dip. For HCHO and NO₂, a spike was apparent in the column densities during the storm followed by a large decrease for the HCHO and a decrease and an inconclusive variation for the NO₂.

Introduction

Hurricane Dorian was a devastating storm that struck the Great Abaco Island in the Bahamas on September 1st, 2019, at approximately 12:30pm local time. Dorian brought with it winds up to 185mph in speed and gusts up to 220mph as well as 3 feet of rainfall and a storm tide of 20-25

feet, granting it the status of a 'Category 6' hurricane, by wind speeds alone. The storm cost the Bahamas nearly \$3.4 billion in damages, with 70% of the costs coming from the Great Abaco Island. Dorian also cost 69 individuals their lives caused 282 individuals to be labeled as missing as of October 2019. Additionally, over 29,5000 individuals were displaced out of house or home due to the effects of Dorian. While Dorian only lingered over the Bahamas from September 1st through the 3rd, it moved at a slower pace than the average hurricane, traversing the islands at an average of 8mph instead of the typical 11mph. Initially, at landfall on the first, the storm was moving at a speed of only 5mph and covered only a 25 mile distance in the first 24 hours following (Masters).

Dorian's remarkably slow speed represents a trend in recent hurricanes. The Scientific American, in an article entitled "A Review of the Atlantic Hurricane Season of 2019", provides, referring to Dorian and other slow 2019 hurricanes such as Barry and Tropical storm Imelda, "Such storms have grown increasingly common in recent decades, according to research published in 2018 and 2019 by NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) hurricane scientist Jim Kossin. His research found a 17% slowdown in the forward speed of tropical cyclones over land areas of the continental US from 1900 to 2017," (Masters). The article also remarks that the slowness of these storms is largely responsible for the intensity of their destructive force. In the Union of Concerned Scientists of the United States' article "Hurricanes and Climate Change", they link this surge of slow moving, catastrophic storms to climate change, arguing that the increase of ocean temperatures and rising sea levels help form this type of storm. The article warns, "Scientists project that, on average, tropical cyclones and hurricanes will have higher wind speeds and higher precipitation rates... The projected increase

in intense hurricanes is substantial -- a doubling or more in the frequency of category 4 or 5 storms by the end of the century -- with the western North Atlantic experiencing the largest increase,” (“Hurricanes and Climate Change”). While any high-force, hurricane winds can cause remarkable devastation by weaponizing debris and spreading mold, the increase in severity of the storm tides and surges produced by these “mega-hurricanes” could easily reach the level of a humanitarian crisis, as seen in the Bahamas after Dorian or in Puerto Rico after category 4 Hurricane Maria struck in 2017 (Schwartz).

Previous hurricanes have been known to also bring with them waves of air pollution, giving cause to the question of why the air quality impact of Dorian should be considered. Hurricane Harvey, which ravaged Texas in 2017, triggered Houston’s worst day for ground-level ozone, or smog, just five days after Harvey began to flood the city, and the conditions persisted in severity for nearly three days (Tresaugue). This could be related to an increase in Nitrogen Dioxide levels in the atmosphere due to the storm, since NO₂ plays a role in the development of smog. Additionally, NO₂ is known to inflame the lining of lungs and interact with other chemicals to form acid rain, (“Basic Information about Carbon Monoxide”). Other pollutants that could be spread with these high force winds include carbon monoxide, aerosols, and formaldehyde. Long term exposure to CO can result in serious health complications, like organ and brain damage. While high levels of CO are not typical outdoors, extenuating circumstances can increase their levels, and even slightly elevated levels of CO can directly affect individuals with heart disease (“Basic Information about Carbon Monoxide”). Aerosols can travel massive distances, despite only being suspended in the atmosphere for 4 to 5 days typically, allowing dust plumes from the Sahara to frequently plague the Atlantic (Simmon). Since coarse aerosols, particulate matter

with a diameter greater than or equal to 10 microns, are dangerous to the lungs, these winds are spreading potentially unbreathable air. Moreover, formaldehyde can also irritate the respiratory tract, and with repeated exposure, can even lead to cancer (“Toxic Substances Portal”). These pollutants are incredibly dangerous to human health, so it is important to investigate how hurricanes affect their atmospheric quantities.

The Copernicus Sentinel 5 Precursor Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (S5P TROPOMI) aboard the European Space Agency’s satellite measures and tracks data for various atmospheric elements, useful for investigating climate and air quality. Its purpose is to assist in the improvement of air quality forecasts and to gain better insight into the quantities of certain chemicals present in the atmosphere. To measure the change in air quality over the Bahamas before and after Hurricane Dorian, the products of nitrogen dioxide, formaldehyde, methane, carbon monoxide, and the aerosol index in the 340-380nm and 354-388nm ranges were considered, with positive aerosol indices indicating the presence of significant aerosol loads.

Methods

NASA’s Earth Data collection includes data from the TROPOMI S5P satellite. From this collection, approximately 26 data files containing the Aerosol Index, both in the 340-380 nm range and the 354-388 nm range [OTHER FILES], were downloaded using NASA’s EarthData web service (<https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/search>) to execute this research. The files were specifically chosen to correspond with the approximate region containing the Bahamas, spanning from (27.2 N, -79.8 E) to (20.6 N, -71 E). This pulled up data files containing information for the above mentioned region. Each file contains information for one complete orbit which in the

case of low earth orbit satellites like S5P includes the sunlit part of the globe with a swath of approximately 2500km.

The files from the website are a netCDF format. NetCDF files are convenient for storing multidimensional data and its associated metadata. They are easily parsed using a variety of methods, and it is the standard for the NASA Earth Science Data Standards group. The open source software, Panoply, is a useful tool for visualizing these types of data files, when they represent atmospheric data.

After obtaining the files, the files were opened in the python environment Jupyter Notebook. For the aerosol index data files, the product information corresponding to the latitude, longitude, and data values for the 340-380nm and 354-388nm indices were extracted. For the other pollutants, the vertical column density was extracted instead. The latitude, longitude, time, and qa-values, which indicate which values of the data are useable (greater than 0.8 for the aerosols, 0.5 for the others files, as indicated in the TROPOMI level 2 “readme” files for each molecule) were all necessary to map the pollutant quantities over the region and used to create plots. Since the islands of the Bahamas are dispersed, a region between (23 N, -79.5 -E) and (26 N, -76.5 E) was focused on using a mask to reduce the chance of the data being weighted towards the oceanic portions around the landmasses. A mean was calculated from this restricted portion to represent the average value of the individual pollutants. Maps were generated for each pollutant on each day between August 24th, 2019 to September 10, 2019, with certain days containing two files corresponding to two orbits of the instrument. For simplicity, the data containing more individual elements in the mentioned subregion was chosen to calculate the mean. The means

were then mapped chronologically in order to depict a trend. The means were also normalized mapped as well.

Conclusion and Discussion

The aim of this research was to determine whether or not the pollutant levels are seen to change before and after the presence of Hurricane Dorian. A degree of oscillation was present in the means for each of the pollutants, but there also appears to be some distinct trends. The means can be seen in the following figures:

Normalized Mean Aerosol Index over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 1, Gilchrist 2019)

Mean Aerosol Index over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 2, Gilchrist 2019)

Normalized Mean CO Content over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 3, Gilchrist 2019)

Mean CO Content over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 4, Gilchrist 2019)

Normalized Mean HCHO Content over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 5, Gilchrist 2019)

Mean HCHO Content over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 6, Gilchrist 2019)

Normalized Mean NO2 Content over the Region Enclosed by (26N, -79E) to (23N, -76E)

(Figure 7, Gilchrist 2019)

(Figure 8, Gilchrist 2019)

For aerosols and CO, a dip appears in the levels of pollutants during the first few days after the storm. For HCHO, a significant increase appears during the course of the storm, which later tapers off, and for NO₂, there's a significant increase during the end of the storm, followed by a rather inconclusive decrease and then a sudden increase right between September 9th and 10th. The consistency of the increase between the various pollutants seems to indicate that certain pollutants, particularly CO, HCHO, and aerosols, do seem to increase during or immediately after Dorian. Greater clarity can be given by considering the geographical maps as well:

Presence of Aerosols over the Bahamas on Sunday, September 01, 2019

Presence of Aerosols over the Bahamas on Sunday, September 01, 2019

(Figure 9, Left, and 10, Right, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of Aerosols over the Bahamas on Monday, September 02, 2019

Presence of Aerosols over the Bahamas on Monday, September 02, 2019

(Figure 11, Left, and 12, Right, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of Aerosols over the Bahamas on Tuesday, September 03, 2019

Presence of Aerosols over the Bahamas on Tuesday, September 03, 2019

(Figure 13, Left, and 14, Right, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of CO over the Bahamas on Sunday, September 01, 2019

Presence of CO over the Bahamas on Monday, September 02, 2019

(Figure 15, Left, and 16, Right, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of CO over the Bahamas on Tuesday, September 03, 2019

(Figure 17, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of HCHO over the Bahamas on Sunday, September 01, 2019

(Figure 18, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of HCHO over the Bahamas on Monday, September 02, 2019

(Figure 19, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of HCHO over the Bahamas on Tuesday, September 03, 2019

(Figure 20, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of NO₂ over the Bahamas on Sunday, September 01, 2019

(Figure 21, Gilchrist 2019)

Presence of NO₂ over the Bahamas on Monday, September 02, 2019

(Figure 22, Gilchrist 2019)

(Figure 23, Gilchrist 2019)

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